

Studies on Complex Formation by 2-Aminothiazole with Metal Ions in Aqueous Solution: Evaluation of Enthalpies and Entropies of Complex Formation and Ligand Field Stabilization Energies of the Metal Complexes

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The complexes formed by 2-aminothiazole with Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) in aqueous solution have been investigated pH-metrically; the formation constants at different temperatures (25-40°) have been evaluated using the graphical method of Rossotti and Rossotti. Values of the enthalpies and entropies of complexation in all the cases as well as the ligand field stabilization energies of the Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes have also been evaluated. Bonding mode of 2-aminothiazole has been ascertained by comparing the formation constant values of the complexes of this ligand with those of some other analogous heterocyclic systems.

TRANSITION metal complexes formed by ligands having nitrogen and sulphur donors are of great significance in biological metabolic process and a number of nitrogen and sulphur-containing ligands have been studied which include aliphatic amines containing sulphur^{1a}, cystine^{1b}, mercaptoacetates^{1c}, glutathiones^{2a}, mercaptopurines^{2b} and thiophenols^{2c}.

In view of the increasing recognition of the importance of thiazole group in biological systems Duff *et al*^{3a-c} made an exhaustive study on the co-ordination behaviour of some simple and substituted thiazoles. From the studies on the complexes formed by thiazole⁴ and 2-methyl-benzothiazole⁵ it appears that these form complexes by bonding *via* ring nitrogen. Spectral studies on the allyl substituted thiazole complexes have also been reported^{6a,b}.

Recently Manhas and Bhatia⁷ synthesized the 2-aminothiazole complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Cd(II) and inferred in analogy to 2-aminobenzothiazole that co-ordination is effected by the tertiary nitrogen atom and not by the exocyclic amino group⁸. Joshi *et al*⁹ have studied the effect of substituents on the *pK* values of some substituted thiazoles in mixed solvents.

It is interesting that 2-aminothiazole undergoes intramolecular rearrangement¹⁰ depending on the pH of the solution during complexation with platinum(II) and palladium(II) which is in conformity with the earlier report¹¹ on sulphur-containing heterocycles.

Thermodynamic studies on the complex forma-

tion by transition metal ions with 2-aminothiazole appears worthy of investigation and the results of studies are reported in this paper.

Materials and Methods

2-Aminothiazole, C₃H₄N₂S: The ligand obtained from Koch-light Laboratories Ltd. England was purified further by crystallization from hot benzene after decolorizing the solution with active charcoal and adding petroleum ether to the filtered solution. The purity of the compound was checked by its melting point (92°) and also by elemental analysis.

Found: C, 35.92; N, 3.9; H, 28.1 per cent.
Calcd. for C₃H₄N₂S: C, 36.0; N, 4.0; H, 28.0 per cent.

Stock solutions containing the metal ions were prepared by dissolving the corresponding metal nitrates (G.R, E. Merck or A.R, B.D.H) in doubly distilled water containing a small amount of reagent grade HNO₃ (freed from nitrous fumes by aeration after dilution with water as usual) and were standardized by usual methods as described elsewhere^{1,2}. Potassium nitrate and nitric acid were prepared as described earlier^{1,2}.

All other chemicals used were of reagent quality; distilled water redistilled with a little KMnO₄ and KOH in an all-glass still was used in making all the solutions which were stored in Jena glass vessels.

A Philips pH-meter, PR-9405M (accuracy better than ±0.01) and a Radiometer precision pH-meter, PHM-26 (accuracy better than ±0.005) were used for pH-measurements using glass and calomel

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electrodes. The instruments were first calibrated by the method described earlier^{1,2}.

Evaluation of equilibrium constant for the protonation of the ligand and the formation constants of the complexes :

The equilibrium constant for the protonation of the ligand was evaluated graphically (cf. Figs. 1 and 2 for data at 25°) from measurements of pH values of solutions containing the ligand and HNO₃ in

value of \bar{n} did not exceed 1 even in presence of excess of the ligand under the experimental conditions and hence β_1 and β_2 values have been evaluated at different temperatures from the intercept and slope respectively of the plot of Y_1 vs X_1 (cf. Fig. 2 for data at 25°).

Evaluation of thermodynamic parameters and ligand field stabilization energies :

From the values of the formation constants (β_1

Fig. 1. Protonation and complex formation curves for H⁺-2-aminothiazole and M²⁺-2-aminothiazole systems (25°; μ , 0.1 M); ligand, 0.005 M; M²⁺, 0.001 M in all cases.

different proportions in the manner described earlier^{1,3}. The results indicate that no detectable amount of di- or higher protonated species are formed under the experimental conditions.

From the measured pH values of the solutions containing known concentrations of a metal ion, the ligand (2-aminothiazole) and HNO₃, the value of the formation function \bar{n} , i.e., the average number of moles of the ligand bound per mole of the metal ion, could be evaluated^{1,3}. The formation curves for 25° are shown in Fig. 1 for the different metal complexes. From the \bar{n} values thus obtained for solutions having a particular concentration of metal ion and different concentrations of a ligand the values of the overall formation constants (β_1 and β_2) were evaluated graphically (cf. Figs. 1 & 2 for results at 25°) following the graphical method of Rossotti and Rossotti^{1,4} as described earlier^{1,3}.

From the formation curves of the metal-ligand systems it is seen that in all the cases studied the

and β_2) obtained at different temperatures the enthalpy (ΔH_x) and entropy (ΔS_x) of ligand protonation and complex formation were evaluated graphically from usual plot of $\log \beta_x$ ($x=1, 2$) vs $\frac{1}{T}$.

Using these ΔH_x values the values of the ligand field stabilization energies, δH_1 and δH_2 for the mono- and bis-complexes respectively of the transition metal ions were then evaluated following the method of George and McClure^{1,5}. The $\Delta H'_x$ ($x=1, 2$) values which represent the enthalpy changes in the formation of the complexes in solution from the gaseous metal ion and the ligand in solution have been evaluated from Eq. (1)

$$\Delta H'_x = \Delta H_h + \Delta H_x \quad \dots (1)$$

where ΔH_h is the enthalpy of hydration of the gaseous metal ion.

Results and Discussion

Values of the protonation constant, K_H , and

Fig. 2. Graphical evaluation of protonation constant of 2-aminothiazole and formation constants of metal complexes (25°; μ , 0.1 M);

$$X_1 = \frac{(2-\bar{n})[L]}{(1-\bar{n})}; \quad Y_1 = \frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})[L]}$$

[$p=2$ (for Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+}) and 5 (for H^+); $q=3$ (for Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+}), 4 (for Mn^{2+}) and 5 (for H^+)]

complex formation constants at four different temperatures are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—LIGAND PROTONATION AND METAL-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Cation	Temp. °C	$(\mu=0.1M)$	
		$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2^{(a)}$
H^+	25	5.28	—
	30	5.21	—
	35	5.16	—
	40	5.09	—
Mn^{2+}	25	1.57	5.34
	30	1.41	5.30
	35	1.26	5.26
	40	1.08	5.23
Co^{2+}	25	1.99	4.98
	30	1.88	4.93
	35	1.76	4.90
	40	1.64	4.85
Ni^{2+}	25	2.19	4.86
	30	2.13	4.78
	35	2.07	4.70
	40	2.00	4.60
Cu^{2+}	25	2.42	5.10
	30	2.37	5.02
	35	2.31	4.95
	40	2.26	4.88
Zn^{2+}	25	1.76	4.18
	30	1.72	4.06
	35	1.68	3.91
	40	1.63	3.76
Cd^{2+}	25	1.56	4.19
	30	1.54	4.12
	35	1.51	4.05
	40	1.49	3.98

(a) β_2 values have been evaluated from the slope of the plot $\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})[L]} (=Y_1)$ vs $\frac{(2-\bar{n})[L]}{(1-\bar{n})} (=X_1)$ because \bar{n} values do not exceed 1 even in presence of excess of the ligand under the experimental conditions.

Results of previous studies on pyridine¹⁶ and

2-aminopyridine¹² suggest that in the latter the pyridine ring nitrogen gets protonated rather than the 2-amino nitrogen. In 2-aminothiazole also the ring nitrogen gets protonated and undergoes base strengthening resonance as follows thereby enhancing the protonation constant value :

The formation constant values of the mono complexes of 2-aminothiazole with metal ions follow the sequence $Mn^{2+} < Co^{2+} < Ni^{2+} < Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$ which is well in agreement with the Irving-Williams natural order of stabilities¹⁷ but for the bis-complexes the observed sequence is $Mn^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$. This deviation from the natural sequence of stabilities is presumably due to the fact that the formation constants depend on the ΔH and ΔS values and it is more appropriate to consider the trend in ΔH_x^i , i.e., the enthalpy of complex formation by the gaseous metal ion and the ligand. From the ΔH_x^i values given in Table 2 it appears that both for the mono- and bis-complexes of the bivalent transition metal ions the sequence of $-\Delta H_x^i$ is $Mn^{2+} < Co^{2+} < Ni^{2+} \sim Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$ which is in keeping with the expected trend.

From the values in Table 2 it is also seen that for the mono- and bis-complexes of 2-aminothiazole, Ni^{2+} complexes have the highest δH_x values as expected; for the mono-complexes the order is $Ni^{2+} > Co^{2+} \sim Cu^{2+}$ whereas for the bis-complexes the observed sequence is $Ni^{2+} > Cu^{2+} \sim Co^{2+}$. For octahedral complexes of weak field ligands the values of the ligand field stabilization energies are $8Dq$, $12Dq$ and $6Dq$ for complexes of $Co^{2+}(d^7)$, $Ni^{2+}(d^8)$ and $Cu^{2+}(d^9)$ respectively. However, due to Jahn-Teller distortion $Cu(II)$ complexes are always tetragonal and as a result of this effect the overall stabilization energy of a six co-ordinated $Cu(II)$ complex is often much higher than that of the corresponding complex of $Co(II)$. However, δH_1 and δH_2 values of the mono- and bis-complexes of $Cu(II)$ and $Co(II)$ with 2-aminothiazole are pretty close which suggests that these $Cu(II)$ complexes have a rather medium tetragonal distortion.

In the case of these metal ions investigated the 2-aminothiazole is more likely to bind through nitrogen rather than sulphur. It is therefore necessary to ascertain whether the ring nitrogen or the amino group is involved in the metal binding. On plotting $\log \beta_1$ values for the 2-aminothiazole complexes of these metal vs $\log \beta_1$ values for the 2-aminopyridine complexes¹² a good linear correlation is observed with only the point for Cu^{2+} significantly off the line having intercept zero and slope ca. 0.65 (see Fig. 3, line A). On the other hand, on plotting $\log \beta_1$ for 2-aminothiazole complexes vs $\log \beta_1$ for the imidazole or the pyridine complexes no such good correlation is observed and there is considerable

TABLE 2—VALUES OF ENTHALPY (ΔH , kcal.mole⁻¹), ENTROPY (ΔS , e. u.), FREE ENERGY (ΔG , kcal. mole⁻¹) AT 25° AND LIGAND FIELD STABILIZATION ENERGIES (δH , kcal. mole⁻¹)(a)

Thermodynamic Parameters	H ⁺	Mn ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cd ²⁺
$\Delta H_h^{(b)}$	—	-654	-697	-716	-716.9	-701.1	—
ΔH_1	-5.4	-13.9	-10.0	-5.4	-4.4	-3.6	-1.9
$\Delta H'_1$	—	-667.9	-707	-721.4	-721.3	-704.7	—
ΔS_1	+6.2	-39.4	-24.4	-8.0	-3.6	-4.0	+0.8
ΔG_1	-7.3	-2.2	-2.7	-3.0	-3.3	-2.4	-2.1
δH_1	—	0	24.4	31.4	23.9	0	—
ΔH_2	—	-3.1	-3.3	-7.5	-6.1	-12.0	-6.0
$\Delta H'_2$	—	-657.1	-700.3	-723.5	-723	-713.1	—
ΔS_2	—	+14.1	+11.8	-2.8	+3.0	-21.0	-0.8
ΔG_2	—	-7.3	-6.8	-6.7	-7.0	-5.7	-5.8
δH_2	—	0	20.8	32.7	21.1	0	—

(a) ΔH_x , ΔS_x and ΔG_x values reported here account for log β_x values at the different temperatures (25-40°) within a variation of ± 0.01 of the experimental values.

(b) The values of the enthalpy of hydration (ΔH_h) of the metal ions which were used in calculating the δH_x (x=1, 2) values were obtained from ref. 15.

Fig. 3. log-log plot of the formation constants of some bivalent metal ions with 2-aminothiazole vs. those with 2-aminopyridine, pyridine and imidazole respectively.

A : L=3-aminopyridine (x)
 B : L=Pyridine (Δ)
 C : L=Imidazole (\bullet)

scatter of the points about the best line which can be drawn in each of these cases and these lines have significant intercepts (see Fig. 3, lines B & C). This seems to suggest the binding through amino group of 2-aminothiazole in the complexes of all these metals except perhaps for Cu²⁺ which may be bonded through sulphur and hence deviates perceptibly from the straight line relationship observed in the case of other metal ions.

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